

Australian Research Data Commons

Designing Our Future Activity Plan (Extract) January 2024 - June 2025 (18 months)

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Contents

Introduction	1
ARDC Strategy on a Page	2
Structure of this Activity Plan	3
Strategic Pillars Focus Areas and Activities	4
People Research Data Commons	4
FAIR Assets	5
Secure Access	6
Integration	7
Advanced Analytics	8
Disease Applications	8
Health Service Applications	8
Planet Research Data Commons	9
Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains (TEDISCs)	9
Integrated FAIR Datasets and Services	10
Planet Infrastructure	11
Indigenous Data Governance and Skills	11
Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons	12
Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities (IIRC)	12
Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA)	13
Social Sciences	14
Connections	14
Australian Internet Observatory	15
Australian Creative Histories and Futures	16

Budgets and other activities, including Translational Research Data Challenges, services such as the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud and National Information Infrastructure, Research Link Australia, and policy have been removed from this extract document.

Introduction

PURPOSE

To provide Australian researchers with competitive advantage through data.

MISSION

To accelerate research and innovation by driving excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of high-quality data assets.

Funded by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS), the purpose of the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) is to provide researchers with competitive advantage through data. We're accelerating Australian research and innovation by driving excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of high-quality data assets. To date, the ARDC has partnered with collaborators across academia, government and industry to meet this challenge by building leading-edge digital infrastructure. This type of infrastructure has moved beyond the realm of innovators and early adopters to become an indispensable part of the research ecosystem. We must now ensure that we meet this need with enduring infrastructure and that researchers have the skills and expertise to use it.

A Thematic Research Data Commons (Thematic RDC) is a vehicle for the ARDC and our national partners to collaboratively develop and deliver sustainable digital research infrastructure on a national scale. It will enable us to best meet the needs of our diverse national research communities in a strategic and comprehensive way.

The Thematic RDCs will be enduring initiatives, with the digital research infrastructure capabilities being sustained and enhanced over the long term. Thematic RDCs will be underpinned by the ARDC's unique services in National Information Infrastructure and the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud. Our Outreach team will work to ensure that researchers are engaged with the development of the RDCs and have the skills to use the infrastructure. The development of the Thematic RDCs is underpinned by our values.

We tackle **ambitious** data infrastructure challenges that only we can solve.

Clarity of **focus** enables us to maximise our impact.

Building strong partnerships and **collaborations** is at the heart of everything we do.

We celebrate diversity and recognise **flexibility** is a strength.

Our approach is founded on openness and **transparency**.

The updated strategy on a page (extract below) includes four priority areas for the period of this plan: Thematic RDCs, the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud, National Information Infrastructure and Skills.

ARDC Strategy on a Page

Strategic Drivers

Underpinning Activities

Structure of this Activity Plan

This Activity Plan - Designing Our Future - sets out the Focus Areas and Activities for each of the Strategic Pillars. The first 6 months of the plan include significant co-design activities across the Thematic RDCs. Further detail may be added in future versions of the document.

The plan then sets out the Activities for Services (National Information Infrastructure and Nectar Research Cloud), followed by Research Link Australia and Policy. Budgets for Services and Policy (along with Operations) are included in the ARDC's baseline operating funds and not shown separately.

Details of staff allocation to Activities will be provided as an appendix to the document. It is expected that this profile will be refined and updated throughout the life of the Activity Plan.

The Activity Plan includes the detail necessary to define the programs of work for the Outreach Business Unit (Engagements, Communications and Skills) in support of delivery of the ARDC's strategy.

Strategic Pillars Focus Areas and Activities

People Research Data Commons

The People Research Data Commons (People RDC) starts with the four digital health research challenges identified in consultation: data discovery; secure access; data integration; and advanced analytics. For each challenge, national frameworks are developed through a co-design process. Coordinated strategic implementation projects in each challenge area then commence, focusing on data from three key sources: health studies (academic); the health system (government); and national facilities (NCRIS). Once significant capability in the People RDC digital health challenge areas is built, the later years of the program apply that capability holistically to health service improvement and to addressing disease areas.

People Research Data Commons

1 - FAIR Assets

The data that health researchers need is distributed across government, research and health service sectors. Researchers and innovators face challenges knowing whether and where such data exists, and if so, how to access it. This Focus Area makes findable and accessible the health data, software and models that researchers need to make positive changes to healthcare.

For example, to dynamically update dietary guidelines on stroke management, we want to be sure we have the data we need, that it is governed and standardised for re-use, and that we can find it and request permission to use it.

1.1 National Discovery Framework

The National Discovery Framework describes a nationally consistent set of informatics practices (metadata, identifiers, vocabularies, metadata syndication) to enable a national view of data for health research. ARDC partners from academia, government, NCRIS, health services and industry can facilitate national discovery of their digital assets for health research by adopting and adapting these guidelines.

Health Data Australia will serve as a national aggregation point of metadata about data for health research from academia, government, NCRIS, and health services.

1.2 Health Studies Australian National Data Assets (HeSANDA) (Academic Health Studies)

The academic research sector (including faculties of medicine, medical research institutes and clinician researchers) creates valuable data through its research processes. This Activity supports the efficient collection, management and sharing of that data to help compile the evidence needed to improve healthcare. Particular focus areas include:

- Data from investigator-led clinical trials (interventional studies)
- Data from cohort studies and registries (observational studies)
- Enabling initiatives (national approaches to consent, ethics, standards, policy etc.)
- Catalysing secondary use of data through communities of practice
- Supporting data custodians through communities of practice

1.3 Government Data Assets

To analyse and help improve the health system, researchers depend on data from the federal and state governments who operate it, as well as the local health services that deliver it. While most government health agencies holding research-relevant data are set up to deliver or regulate healthcare, they are not equipped for data provision to researchers. In this Activity, the ARDC will work systematically with three key agencies to improve data access for health researchers:

1. The Australian Institute of Health and Welfare - extension and optimisation of research access systems and processes.
2. The Department of Health and Aging - definition and management of informal research access pathways.
3. The Australian Digital Health Agency - support for ADHA's legislative mandate to develop a scheme for access to My Health Record.

1.4 NCRIS National Data Assets

The ARDC's NCRIS partners create valuable data for health research through the operation of their facilities. Often these NCRIS facilities are spread across multiple nodes operated at research organisations (e.g. universities). In this Activity, the ARDC will work with these disparate facilities to make the data findable and accessible as a national data asset to support leading-edge research. By working across the facilities, the ARDC will help make the national digital infrastructure consistent in its standards for data collection, curation and access.

Working with all the NCRIS health facilities, this Activity will initially focus on bringing data together from multiple university based nodes (e.g. Bioplatforms Australia, National Imaging Facility and Phenomics Australia).

1.5 Underpinning Capabilities

Researchers are busy people with many academic and administrative responsibilities. They need tools, infrastructure and services to make it easy to collect, manage, use and share FAIR data. In some cases, the ARDC will catalyse a national network of consistent institutional capabilities, and in others, it will operate a central national capability.

This Activity provides the resources for nationally supported data collection, storage and secure access for health researchers. It relies on previous consultation via the HeSANDA and Secure Access activities.

People Research Data Commons

2 - Secure Access

Health information of patients and research subjects must be kept secure and not disclosed during the process of health research or health service improvement. Therefore, data custodians require researchers to use secure environments for data analysis. Researchers don't always have secure environments for the data they want to share or access, or when such secure environments exist, they can create data silos that hinder national-scale multidisciplinary collaborations.

This Focus Area has an important touchpoint with Focus Area 4, Advanced Analytics, whereby federated machine learning leaves data within the custodian's trusted research environment (e.g. NSW Health Department) and takes the query to the data. Standardised procedures supported by a number of TREs will be an important enabler of national scale research over secure data ('data visiting').

2.1 National TRE Framework

This Activity is establishing a national framework for trusted research environments (TREs). This is in response to explicit calls from the sector for the ARDC to broker a national conversation around the core features of an TRE, a reference architecture, and principles to underpin consistency and interoperability. The ARDC is harnessing expertise from a number of previous trusted research environment projects such as SERP, ERICA and CADRE.

The framework will provide a common blueprint and best practice guidelines for use by, for example, the many universities and research institutions currently building their own capability for institutional accreditation under the ONDC's Data Scheme. It will also lay the foundation for a network of secure access services.

2.2 Network of Secure Access Services (Health Studies)

This Activity will establish a network of secure access services that are 'conformant' to the National TRE Framework. The network aims to provide TRE coverage for secondary use of data in strategic areas of academic research (clinical trials, cohorts etc.).

2.3 Network of Secure Access Services (Government)

Government agencies operate TREs, and as such, they are also part of the network of secure access services that researchers would like to be consistent, appropriate, interoperable and comprehensive for the data they need for research. In partnership with government agencies, this Activity will catalyse consistency between government and research systems and processes.

2.4 Network of Secure Access Services (NCRIS)

Within NCRIS facilities there is a wide variety of operational models for TREs spanning from, for example, PHRN's direct funding of secure data linkage units, through to Phenomics Australia's dependency on university node partners. NCRIS facilities are key stakeholders in the operation of important TREs and are part of the network of secure access services that researchers would like to be consistent, appropriate, interoperable and comprehensive for the data they need for research. In partnership with NCRIS facilities, this Activity will catalyse consistency between NCRIS, government and broader research systems and processes.

People Research Data Commons

3 - Integration

To solve the grand challenges facing society, researchers seek insights by combining data from government, research and health service providers. Since this data is collected in a wide range of scientific, business or operational contexts, it uses different standards and structures, which makes it difficult for researchers to bring the data together.

For example, to improve outcomes for people who suffer traumatic injuries in car accidents, we want to integrate data from the trauma registry, car accident insurance claims, accident and emergency hospital records, ambulance records, research studies, and the deaths registry.

This Focus Area will promote and support across these sources the use of any existing national and international standards for data structures, common medical concept definitions, and common identifiers for concepts, people, resources, etc.

3.1 National Semantic Interoperability Framework

Data is valuable when it can be joined up with other data to provide new insights. In particular, joining local health studies to large population datasets provides great value. Common data models, common ontologies, and common identifiers allow data to be joined up more easily, and yet doing the 'right thing' in this area can be confusing, hard and expensive. This Framework outlines opportunities for data generators in research or healthcare to easily adopt community standards to make their data more valuable.

3.2 Research Tools Semantic Standards

Researchers who collect data during the course of a health study need survey and data collection tools to make collecting data according to community standards easy. This Activity will work with tool developers to support national and international or community appropriate standards at the point of data collection.

3.3 National Semantic Standards

Integrating research studies, such as clinical trials and cohort studies, with public sector administrative datasets can be time consuming for all parties. This Activity will establish streamlined and enduring approaches to this currently ad hoc activity.

A good deal of state level and health service level data can be standardised to common data models to enable research, analysis and integration. This Activity will set up national level approaches to common data models that will be further scaled up in 2025 via the Health Service Applications Focus Area (6). Enabling infrastructure for discovering and querying such standardised data will be established.

3.4 Semantic Interoperability for NCRIS

To support Activity 1.4 (NCRIS national data assets), common ontologies and data models will be developed to enable federated datasets to operate as national data assets across universities and NCRIS facilities.

People Research Data Commons

4 - Advanced Analytics

Applying advanced analytics techniques like machine learning to national-scale sensitive data collections across multiple secure data repositories raises data challenges that require innovative solutions. With the naturally siloing effect of sensitive data, it is a challenge to achieve the scale desirable for data science.

4.1 National Infrastructure Framework for Health Analytics

The Australian Data Science Network is a collaboration of 34 data science research groups around Australia. In 2024, the ARDC is working with ADSN to publish a framework for infrastructure to support AI in health research. The Framework will document and prioritise AI infrastructure needs in the following areas: Underpinning Hardware Infrastructure; National Reference Data Assets; Underpinning Federation Infrastructure; Tools; Skills, Policy & Support. A demonstrator will be developed in parallel with the Framework to test and illustrate some of these components. This will inform a portfolio of coordinated projects implementing the Framework across the People RDC in following years.

4.2 Pilot Research AI Applications

In 2024-25, the ARDC will run a coordinated set of pilot projects to implement various aspects of the National Infrastructure Framework for Health Analytics with universities, medical research institutes, and national research collaborations. This could be focused to include MRFF projects where ARDC is a collaborator, previous ARDC partnerships, or scenarios from the HeSANDA activity (1.2) .

4.3 Pilot Government AI Applications

In 2024-25, the ARDC will run a coordinated set of pilot projects to implement various aspects of the National Infrastructure Framework for Health Analytics with government data custodians. Researchers are keen to apply advanced analytics to federal, state and local health service data. However, these organisations are set up to operate and regulate the health system; they are not equipped, for example, to participate in federated machine learning or create synthetic datasets. Activity projects will be pathfinders for government participation in advanced analytics for research, which will follow on to projects in Health Service Applications Focus Area (6).

4.4 Pilot NCRIS AI Applications

In 2024-25, the ARDC will run a coordinated set of pilot projects to implement various aspects of the National Infrastructure Framework for Health Analytics with NCRIS facilities. For example, machine learning over medical imaging or large genomic datasets to support diagnostics and therapeutics development are areas of focus for some NCRIS facilities.

5 - Disease Applications

Years 3-5 of the People RDC will see a small set of large coordinated projects address diseases, such as cancer and dementia, combining all four data challenge areas (discovery, secure access, integration and advanced analytics). These projects will leverage the capability established in the first two years.

5.1 Diseases TBD (cancer, dementia, cardiovascular)

No co-investment activity is scheduled for this 18-month Activity Plan.

6 - Health Service Applications

Years 3-5 of the People RDC will see a coordinated set of projects combining all four data challenge areas applied to health service improvement. Common data models applied to state level health services will open up heterogeneous hospital records data to analysis at national and even international scale, while research embedded into local health services is naturally translational since researchers are working directly on the problems of service delivery using advanced analytics and data integration in trusted research environments.

6.1 Areas TBD (state and local services)

No co-investment activity is scheduled for this 18-month Activity Plan.

Planet Research Data Commons

The Planet RDC is addressing priority data challenges and making earth and environmental sciences data and models more integrated, accessible and interoperable on a national scale. It is explicitly working between research, government and industry sectors to develop research translation pathways.

The Planet RDC will develop national enduring infrastructure platforms and services. This will include the establishment of appropriate governance structures, and a focus on monitoring, evaluation and team building and service delivery.

During 2024, the Planet RDC will undertake preparation for anticipated 2025 activities, including alignment with the Department of Education's Climate and Environment, NDRI Strategy and Research Translation Step Change activities. This will involve network and partnership development, and scoping of the National Environmental Data Lake (2.4) and the AI ready program (2.5) activities.

1 - Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains (TEDISCs)

The need for trusted environmental data and information supply chains is paramount. Researchers require accurate and dependable data to conduct their studies and derive valid conclusions. Governments need reliable data for policy-making, environmental management, and regulatory compliance. Industries require trustworthy data for environmental impact assessments, sustainable resource management, and to meet regulatory standards.

Australia has many excellent producers of data. However, there is currently no whole-of-system approach to overcome the challenges of discovering and accessing data, the costliness of making it interoperable, and its limited scalability. This Focus Area will develop a system-wide approach by:

- Supporting a common view of the capabilities in earth and environmental science data and information supply chains, enabling better alignment of effort and interoperability.
- Increasing trust mechanisms across the earth and environmental sectors to facilitate increased data flows between research, government and industry.

1.1 Exemplar Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains

This Activity explicitly focuses on cross-sector (research, government and industry) specific regional areas for which trusted data and information supply chains need to be developed. The focus on regions is warranted as environmental systems and cumulative impacts are understood and assessed on a regional scale. At least three regional projects will be developed in areas with high biodiversity values and development pressures, and will cover a range of ecosystem types, pressures and stakeholder communities. A co-design partnership approach will be used to develop projects involving stakeholders from research, government and industry.

Planet Research Data Commons

2 - Integrated FAIR Datasets and Services

Being able to understand, predict and manage changes to the environment requires continental scale observations backed by a strong observation network that is integrated and interoperable. However, finding, accessing and standardising data for cross-domain analysis is still resource intensive. Data is often too disparate and heterogeneous to be easily interoperable. The provision of a single entry point to FAIR data, alongside next generation storage and repository services, is needed to realise the Planet RDC vision.

This Focus Area will equip data stewards with the tools and capability to enable long-tail data to be made FAIR to enable integration for knowledge creation.

2.1 National-scale Integrated Datasets and Services

This Activity will focus on the creation and retention of national scale integrated and standardised datasets that meet specific research needs. Research in the environment is still constrained by access to nationally consistent and available data. This data is often only accessible through manual request processes to government jurisdictions and individual university research centre collections. Examples include a National Tree Growth dataset (derived from university and forestry records) and species trait data and state of the environment reporting datasets.

Catalysing the development of national significant datasets identified through the national consultation process, participating partners will be required to ensure datasets are able to be maintained and updated, and utilise ARDC

2.2 Domain Data Portals

National consultation has indicated that research is being hampered by the ability to find and discover domain and discipline related data. This Activity will build the capacity to systematically create national 'federated data portals' for partner organisations or specific disciplines using Research Data Australia. It will utilise best-practice meta-data description and will align with the National PID strategy and Research Data Australia to enable a consolidated view. Activities will focus on the National Environmental Science Program (NESP), which is Australia's largest long-term environmental research program covering four domain areas and 37 universities.

2.3 Interoperability Uplift + FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)

Commencing in 2025, this Activity is aimed at supporting data management and research communities in identifying and incentivising cross-domain interoperability capability and uplift in data standards. It will adopt the CODATA WorldFAIR approach and work with research communities and the National Earth and Environmental Facilities Forum (NEESFF) to design, develop and adopt five draft FIPs relevant to domains of marine, terrestrial, biodiversity, atmosphere and freshwater.

2.4 National Environmental Data Lake

No co-investment activity is scheduled for this 18-month Activity Plan.

2.5 AI Ready Program

No co-investment activity is scheduled for this 18-month Activity Plan.

Planet Research Data Commons

3 - Planet Infrastructure

Virtual research environments, research platforms and data visualisation tools empower researchers to collaborate with national and international partners in modelling and data analysis. They provide streamlined access to data, advanced analytic tools and compute resources, and encourage repeatable workflows. Platforms that combine user interfaces with trusted models and data are needed to enable research and its translation into decision making and management.

However, differing technical architectures restrict interoperability and integration between platforms, hindering multidisciplinary research. Additionally, these research platforms are often developed using project or grant funding and ongoing sustainability is a challenge, as is access to appropriately skilled technical staff.

This Focus Area will provide national coordination of shared digital infrastructure and reference architectures to significantly enhance the capability of research communities to deploy modelling and analytic platforms at scale. Support will also be provided to enable the reuse of scientific models, and the ability to network between models to encourage multidisciplinary research.

3.1 Modelling, Analytics and Decision Support Infrastructure (platforms) (MADSI)

This Activity is aimed at meeting research and government needs to discover, run and network trusted analytical and modelling tools and outputs. It will develop enduring national infrastructure and services by building on and supporting current Planet RDC transition platforms (EcoCommons, Biosecurity Commons and AgreFed). This will enable faster and more efficient deployment of cloud-based modelling, analytics (e.g. R, python, AI/ML workflows) and decision-support capabilities (e.g. decision tools, data visualisation). Projects under the MADSI program will have shared governance and reference architectures to develop a cohesive Planet RDC ecosystem at scale.

3.2 National Machine-based Observation Data Infrastructure and Pipelines

Developing national data infrastructure, pipelines and data to enable continental scale monitoring and trend analysis, this Activity will focus on conservation technologies including camera traps, acoustic recorders and drones. It will support the operation of national platforms for EcoAcoustics, Australian Scalable Drone Cloud, and Camera Traps; develop a National Support and Data Synthesis Capability; and institute a dedicated storage and high throughput computing pipeline.

3.3 Multi-cloud Data Environments

No co-investment activity is scheduled for this 18-month Activity Plan.

4 - Indigenous Data Governance and Skills

Indigenous knowledge is essential to caring for Country (land, sea and water), and therefore to protecting and restoring Australia's natural environment. The Planet RDC will work with NCRIS partners to implement a common best practice approach to Indigenous knowledge management. This includes implementing the CARE principles (Collective Benefit; Authority to Control; Responsibility and Ethics) for Indigenous Data Governance, which was endorsed during the consultation process as foundational for the Planet RDC.

4.1 Indigenous Data Governance and Sovereignty, and Implementing CARE Principles

Earth and environmental research infrastructure providers and research organisations will build capability in Indigenous Data Sovereignty and CARE principles. This will be achieved through a co-investment learning partnerships project involving National Earth and Environmental Facilities Forum (NEESFF) organisations to: audit and review the Indigenous data held by their organisation and related policies; and conduct a baseline audit of the CARE principles and their application. It will involve the HASS&I RDC and external partnerships (IDN/CSIRO) for implementation.

4.2 Digital Training Frameworks for Researchers, NRI and Governments

Developing national training frameworks for researchers, national research infrastructure providers and government, this Activity aims to make training more consistent and national.

5-Year Budget

Planet RDC is funded to June 2025. Additional funding will be requested through the Federal Government's 2024 Research Infrastructure Investment Plan.

Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons is harnessing research data to enhance Australian social and cultural wellbeing, and help Australia understand and preserve our culture, history and heritage. The HASS&I RDC is committed to enabling capable people, effective institutions, innovative technology, relevant data and collaborative governance with the aim of elevating research capability in the HASS and Indigenous research sectors.

From January 2024 to June 2025, the HASS&I RDC will be focussed on contracting co-investment activities associated with all six focus areas, and delivering on events associated with cohering a community of HASS researchers.

1 - Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities (IIRC)

[Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities](#) celebrates, supports and enhances the capabilities of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and researchers at the interface of research data science and Indigenous knowledge systems. It builds on and extends national and international frameworks of Indigenous Data Governance (IDG) and Indigenous Data Sovereignty (IDS) to collectively strengthen the foundations of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander data governance principles. Working with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander data custodians, IIRC focuses on how Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities engage with, and what they aspire for, in the governance of their data.

Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities is contracted through to 30 June 2024. In February 2024, work will begin to co-design a second phase to commence from July 2024.

1.0 Indigenous Data Governance and Sovereignty

Demonstrate what Indigenous knowledge and research data governance looks like through the development of a diverse portfolio of projects that utilise Indigenous Data Governance frameworks within community-controlled and government agencies. This diverse stakeholder pool will be brought together in a roundtable setting to share learning and drive consensus approaches to Indigenous data governance.

1.1 Indigenous Data Catalogue and Extensions

Expand the [Indigenous Data Network Data Catalogue \(IDNC\)](#) to exemplify both the proper handling of Indigenous data, as well as what is considered in scope as 'Indigenous data' from an Indigenous data governance perspective. Secure and catalogue the Indigenous data held by Australian universities for the benefit of Indigenous communities.

1.2 Indigenous Spatio-temporal Frameworks and Infrastructure

Enhance Indigenous data representations through the application of fuzzy mapping methods and the production of an [Indigenous Data Mapping Interface](#).

1.3 Data Capability Building for Digital Futures in Indigenous Australia

Upskill champion-researchers to spread knowledge and understanding of Indigenous data governance, support the development of research data literacy and management within Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities and organisations, and drive international Indigenous data upskilling through a global classrooms initiative.

1.4 Indigenous Data Repositories and Rematriation

Investigate and implement culturally appropriate and sustainable data storage options for Indigenous data collections. Pursue opportunities for rematriation of Indigenous data (i.e., the returning of data of many kinds to the country or community of origin), including across international borders. In doing so, the Activity will build global recognition of Australian leadership in these initiatives.

Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons

2 - Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA CA)

Australia is a massively multilingual country in one of the world's most linguistically diverse regions. [The Language Data Commons of Australia \(LDA CA\)](#) is developing an integrated national technical infrastructure for analysing language collections at scale in order to open up the social and economic possibilities of Australia's rich linguistic and cultural heritage. LDA CA ensures long-lasting access for the analysis and reuse of invaluable language data, managing the data in a culturally, ethically and legally appropriate manner guided by FAIR and CARE principles.

2.0 Project Management

The Language Data Commons of Australia is contracted through to 30 June 2024. In February 2024, work will begin to co-design a second phase to commence from July 2024.

2.1 Social, Data and Technology Architecture of the LDA CA Archival Data Repository

Produce frameworks for sustainable language data governance and for a comprehensive language data policy and procedures. Produce a suite of tools and services for language archiving, accessing sensitive linguistic data and to enable donation of linguistic data.

2.2 Securing Language Data Collections

Build out a portfolio of language data demonstrating the breadth and depth of linguistic riches available in Australia and its region, including Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander language data, Indigenous language data in Australia's Pacific region, Australian English and migrant language data collections, and sign language data collections in Australia and its region.

2.3 Increasing Accessibility of Language Data for Researchers and Communities through LDA CA Data Portal

Enable discovery and annotation of a range of digital collections held in Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAM) institutions, including oral history collections and other specialist language data collections. Improve machine-access to national language data collections for advanced analysis.

2.4 Improving Language and Text Data Analysis Environments for Researchers and Communities

Establish an integrated analytics environment for researchers to create fully described, reproducible research on written, spoken, multimodal and signed text in accordance with Open Science principles, and aligned with community expectations for research of practical benefit.

2.5 Strategic Partnerships, Engagement and Training

Provide training and develop resources for researchers and communities to support best practice in accessing, analysing and archiving language data in line with FAIR and CARE principles. Scope strategic engagement with key international, national and community partners. Increase the engagement of Australian researchers and communities with the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA CA).

Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons

3 - Social Sciences

The ARDC will run a pilot activity to determine leadership of the Social Sciences Focus Area. A broader program of work in the social sciences will be developed from March 2024.

3.1 Project Management

Work is currently underway to co-design the six-month pilot, which will improve metadata for social sciences data related to disadvantaged Australians.

4 - Connections

HASS and Indigenous research communities harness research data to enhance Australian social and cultural wellbeing, and help Australia understand and preserve our culture, history and heritage. However, these communities conduct research in such disparate ways - a key challenge for the HASS&I RDC is to align researchers with both the aims of the RDC, as well as with new and larger communities. The Connections Focus Area seeks to join-up historically closed communities of practitioners. The activities are designed to bring together researchers from across this spectrum and create scenarios that allow them to identify common interests and potential collaborators.

4.1 Community Data Lab

The Community Data Lab seeks to surface areas of interest and potential collaboration across disciplinary boundaries, focusing on common sources of data (such as the National Library's Trove), common methodologies (e.g. the application of advance text analytics), or a common structural challenge (such as the need to disseminate analysed or annotated data for consumption by the general public).

The initial focus for 2024 is consolidating existing work in the Community Data Lab, before transforming it from a pilot to a co-investment activity. In doing so, it will consider a broader range of GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) involvement, beyond the national libraries Trove aggregator service.

4.2 Securing Data

Identify and act on at risk data. This data is usually identified during the course of running other activities within other focus areas under the HASS&I RDC.

4.3 Exposing GLAM Data to HASS and Indigenous Researchers

Securing and exposing GLAM data access addresses common structural concerns for the sector. Identifying and prioritising what GLAM data needs to be secured and what would benefit from greater exposure requires vision and leadership. This Activity will identify and act to expose data of high value to a broad cross-section of the HASS and Indigenous research community. This data is usually identified during the course of running other activities within other HASS&I RDC Focus Areas.

4.4 Governance of Indigenous Data and Indigenous Data Governance

Coordinate across activities in other focus areas to ensure a consistent and harmonious approach to governance of Indigenous data (i.e. ensuring that Indigenous people are involved in the governance of any and all data), and Indigenous data governance (i.e. ensuring that proper governance is established for data identified as impacting upon Indigenous people or communities).

4.5 Access and Authentication

A common structural challenge faced by the academic community is breaking down the barriers to access and involvement of the wider community, for example, citizen scientists or Indigenous communities. In addressing this challenge, this Activity will identify and document requirements across all HASS&I infrastructures for a common layer of access and authentication. It will include designing a common 'front door' for the RDC as part of digital place making.

Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons

5 - Australian Internet Observatory

Under the Australian Internet Observatory Focus Area, the Australian Social Data Observatory (ASDO) will develop a national system for curating and analysing social and human behaviour data from diverse sources. Associated activities will provide the skills and training needed for a new generation of researchers across all disciplines to use and analyse social data, providing real-time understanding of diverse contexts and complex social, cultural and economic issues.

5.1 Social Data Sources

Develop technologies and approaches to data donation and crowd-sourced data to enable data collection that cannot otherwise be harvested directly from closed social platforms and similar. Accelerate the process of web scraping through technical and skills-based activities. Demonstrate and spread the benefits of synthetic data generation to preserve privacy when analysing personal data, especially for social media data.

5.2 Social Data Analytics Platforms

Leverage the application of readily available tools to enhance collections, especially for automated speech to text, entity recognition, image recognition and labelling, crowd sourced annotation or labelling. Shift workloads from desktop to secure cloud based approaches.

5.3 Data Classification and Linking

Support the input, curation and preservation of 'messy' data to be converted into more robust, archival-quality data. Where necessary, support this with the development of new metadata standards and protocols to increase efficiency and usability of social data.

5.4 Governance, Training and Engagement

Explore and test the many ethical, legal and standardisation issues presented by social data research. Develop national and international guidelines for best practice, including the adoption of FAIR and CARE principles. Establish relevant governance groups including Steering committee, user reference groups and project management committee. Provide training, tools and guides for Australian researchers. Provide extensive opportunities for engagement and collaboration with government, industry and civil society organisations.

Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons

6 - Australian Creative Histories and Futures

The Australian Creative Histories and Futures Focus Area will create a much stronger foundation for preserving and studying the aesthetic and economic contributions that the arts make to Australian culture. It will provide a greater opportunity to more easily research across art forms, and outline a clearer sense of the factors that have shaped trends and fault-lines in Australian arts practice.

This Focus Area will enhance the interoperability between AustLit (literature) and AusStage (performing arts), the two largest, most sophisticated, mature, and best-known datasets in the Australian cultural context. Doing so presents an opportunity to facilitate and encourage exploration between and across these datasets and collections to produce more profound and creative searches, across a broader range of disciplines and research paradigms.

6.1 National Arts API

Develop a common web-based Application Programming Interface (API) for project partners that will enable a diverse range of users to make queries across both databases at the same time, as well as contribute new records where it makes sense. Demonstrate data analysis and visualisation capability delivered by a common API.

6.2 New Data Ontologies

Compare existing ontologies and data models and take tangible steps towards interoperability and enrichment of partner datasets. Generate consensus and a common implementation to capture non-binary approaches to gender and inclusive description of disability. Augment existing metadata to surface Indigenous materials already held in partner collections.

6.3 Harvesting Born-Digital Data

Address sustainability issues inherent in both collections by identifying opportunities to automate the harvest and organise born-digital arts data, ideally leveraging the API developed in 6.1. Partner with GLAM organisations and industry aggregators to ensure that their data flows become part of the data collections via an 'archive as you go' approach.

6.4 Embedding Citizen Science

Produce a series of skills and community building activities to drive uptake of developed services by citizen services, through a 'communities of practice' building approach. Establish mechanisms for community identification of possible future service enhancements.

6.5 Creative Use of Creative Data

Collaborate with digital artists and data scientists to transform how data can be presented and used and to generate new ways to think about creative histories data in the future.